

CHOOSING TEACHING METHODS FOR INSTRUCTING ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS

Sodikova O.

UzSWLU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880892>

Abstract. *Teaching English to young learners requires a careful selection of approaches that align with their cognitive, emotional, and linguistic development. This article explores various teaching methods suitable for young learners, highlighting the importance of creating an engaging, interactive, and supportive learning environment. It examines the role of play-based learning, storytelling, songs, and games as effective tools for language acquisition. Additionally, the article emphasizes the significance of adapting teaching methods to cater to the diverse needs, interests, and learning styles of children, ensuring a more inclusive and motivating experience. By integrating a variety of approaches, educators can foster a positive attitude towards language learning, making the process both enjoyable and effective for young learners.*

Keywords: *young learners, English language teaching, teaching methods, cognitive development, play-based learning, storytelling.*

English for Young Learners refers to teaching English to children in pre-primary or primary (elementary) school who do not speak English as their first language. This includes children whose native language is the national language of their country, where they learn English as an additional language. In today's globalized world, challenges such as population movement, differences between isolated rural communities and diverse urban areas, and attitudes towards minorities—both indigenous and newly arrived—impact the process of teaching English to young learners. As a result, teaching English as a second language to young learners has attracted considerable attention in recent years.

The early years of childhood are vital for language acquisition, and offering high-quality language education during this period can significantly influence a child's language abilities and overall cognitive growth. Consequently, it is important to investigate effective strategies and techniques for teaching English to young learners. In today's globalized society, the ability to communicate proficiently in English is becoming ever more crucial. Introducing English language instruction at a young age can help children build strong language skills and promote cultural awareness.

Primary school teachers primarily focus on teaching the fundamentals of English as part of the curriculum. One of the foundational aspects that students learn is vocabulary, which involves understanding a list of words and their meanings. At the primary level, children already possess some knowledge of letters and words, and it is important for them to further develop their basic grammar and vocabulary. Reading storybooks is an excellent way to enhance their comprehension and vocabulary skills. Teaching vocabulary can be effectively done by introducing simple topics, such as everyday objects, names of fruits, animals, sports, games, and by providing instructions.

This paper seeks to explore the most effective practices for teaching English to young learners, taking into account their distinct cognitive abilities and learning styles. The study's research objectives are: (1) to identify materials that are suitable for the age group when teaching English, (2) to investigate engaging teaching methods that encourage active participation and

language acquisition, and (3) to examine the importance of establishing a supportive learning environment for young learners. The paper specifically focuses on teaching English to children aged 3 to 10 years. The research is primarily based on existing literature, with efforts made to incorporate a range of perspectives.

As part of the curriculum issued on May 23, 2006, specifies that English is taught as a local subject starting from elementary school and even in kindergarten. Phillips (2002) suggested that young learners tend to be more holistic learners, engaging with the language based on its practical use and what they can accomplish with it, rather than viewing it as an abstract system or intellectual exercise. Setiaryni (2011) pointed out that young learners not only face challenges with reading and writing skills but also exhibit distinct characteristics in terms of cognitive levels, interests, needs, and environments. To support effective learning for young learners, it is essential to provide activities that are meaningful, purposeful, and enjoyable.

Many teachers have leveraged the Internet and technology to enhance language classrooms, incorporating visual aids and interactive teaching techniques. Today, learners have greater access to a variety of language-learning resources, such as YouTube, Netflix, BBC, TED Talks, news channels, and radio podcasts, allowing them to learn the language and explore content of interest from the comfort of their homes. It is increasingly rare to find a teenager or young adult without a smartphone or Internet access, and this applies to young Vietnamese students as well. The significant rise in high school and university students with YouTube or Netflix accounts, along with the time they spend watching TV shows, viral videos, soap operas, and movies, led the researcher to consider whether these engaging resources could be used to boost learners' motivation and listening skills in ESL classrooms (Ngo & Ha, 2022).

A teaching technique refers to the practical application of a teaching method at the procedural level within the classroom. In some cases, different teaching methods may share similar techniques, although they are required to have distinct techniques as well.

Teachers' practices in English literacy instruction are evident in the teaching techniques they implement during classroom sessions. The findings reveal that all teachers employ similar techniques, such as demonstrating, describing, and using singing strategies. Additionally, it was found that the teachers refrained from using other strategies due to the need for extensive preparation and the challenges they posed for students. These new strategies were considered difficult because they required substantial preparation and could be challenging for the learners.

Furthermore, based on the results of a questionnaire completed by nine teachers of young learners, using a Likert scale to gauge opinions, attitudes, and views, it was observed that the teachers applied specific teaching and learning strategies when instructing English to young learners. The scoring statements included (5) Strongly Agree, (4) Agree, (3) Neutral, (2) Disagree, and (1) Strongly Disagree. The results indicated that the teachers were enthusiastic about teaching English to young learners and viewed introducing English at this level as essential.

Scott (2009) provided valuable and effective guidelines for teaching English to young learners. Activities should incorporate visual aids, such as facial expressions, movements, mime, and pictures, to help learners comprehend what they hear. Scott and Ytreberg (1993) recommended various activities for young learners, including "listen and do" exercises, movement-based activities, miming stories, drawing, using questionnaires, listening for information, "listen and color," "listen and repeat," creating stories, and reading stories.

Teachers should improve the quality of their teaching by developing effective techniques for instructing English to young learners and addressing the various challenges encountered in teaching process. Before selecting teaching techniques, teachers should first understand students' foundational knowledge and skills. It is more effective to use teaching methods that are simple, easy, and engaging. It is recommended that teachers of young learners incorporate games, demonstrations, presentations, as well as the Practice and Production (PPP) approach when teaching English.

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